

D1.1 - Reference document on European AI Lighthouse implementation

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
ADR	AI, Data and Robotics
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AI-aaS	AI-as-a-Service
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EIC	European Innovation Council
EIF	European Investment Fund
EU	European Union
FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
HW	Hardware
IoT	Internet of Things
IP	Intellectual Property
ISS	International Space Station
JPL	Jet Propulsion Laboratory
LLM	Large Language Model
MOOC	Massive Open Online Course
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NoE	Network of Excellence

ODM	Original Design Manufacturer
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OS	Operating System
RISC	Reduced Instruction Set Computer
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SRA	Strategic Research Agenda
SW	Software
TDW	Theme Development Workshop
TEF	Testing and Experimentation Facility
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

Executive Summary

The deliverable D1.1, “Reference document on European AI Lighthouse implementation” presents the European AI Lighthouse under different aspects. It starts by analyzing the policy background leading to the idea of AI lighthouse and the general objectives. The current state of the AI Lighthouse is then presented with a complementary description of the nine pillar projects and the existing additional initiatives contributing to the Lighthouse. The multiple collaboration actions and activities are described, focusing on currently implemented mechanisms. In a second step, novel insights on possible activities to strengthen the AI Lighthouse are presented. These encompass actions for community mobilization, recommendations for increasing visibility, role of upcoming coordination actions, exploitation and sustainability of the AI Lighthouse, and scientific and organizational recommendations to leverage the AI Lighthouse networks. Finally, this document summarizes the novel objectives and suggests a new phase in the AI policy making process.

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1. Introduction

The “Reference document on European AI lighthouse Implementation” is a thorough guide to understanding the European AI Lighthouse initiative. This document aims to provide an overview of the foundation of the AI Lighthouse. It also provides an overview of the collaborative efforts within the AI Lighthouse as it was taking place over time. Furthermore, this document summarizes the objectives of the European AI Lighthouse, and introduces the “pillars” of the lighthouse. By the “pillars” we refer to the Network of Excellence (NoE) projects. The NoE projects form the foundation of the AI Lighthouse, spanning a wide array of domains within the field of Artificial Intelligence. Moreover, the document outlines the strategic framework and policy background and considerations of the AI Lighthouse, emphasizing the importance of transparent, ethical, and human-centric AI principles.

Afterwards, the document provides a comprehensive overview of the collaboration mechanisms between the different networks of excellence, highlighting the importance of such collaborations for achieving the objectives of the AI Lighthouse. Various outcomes from the existing NoEs are presented, including the ecosystem mapping, the Joint research agenda, and other direct outcomes of the NoEs projects. The collaboration approaches developed and employed to facilitate synergy among diverse stakeholders across the NoEs are highlighted and discussed including the community workshops, the communication between the NoEs, and the coordination between them.

Finally, the Recommendations sections encapsulates a series of directives and strategies aimed at steering the AI Lighthouse initiative towards greater impact. Actionable measures are presented with the aim to increase the visibility of the AI Lighthouse to stakeholders across the domain of Artificial intelligence. Also proposing coordination actions with longer duration for ensuring the sustainability of the projects. As the AI Lighthouse accelerates towards its goals, the proposed recommendations serve as guiding beacons, illuminating the path towards a more impactful, human-centric, sustainable, and ethical AI ecosystem in Europe.

2. European AI Lighthouse overview

2.1. Policy background

Key strategic orientations for the development and uptake of Artificial Intelligence (‘AI’) in Europe have been formulated and refined over the past seven years.¹ As evidenced in the joint work carried out by EU Member States and the European Commission, networks of AI research excellence centres have emerged as a key component of research and technological capacity building across Europe.

This new cooperation paradigm was prompted by the European Parliament and the Council which had emphasised, already in 2017, the need for a new European framework for AI technologies and

¹ This section reviews policy making initiatives which have directly shaped the European AI Lighthouse networks. For a comprehensive overview on AI policy making, see AI4Media, ‘D2.1 Overview & Analysis of the AI Policy Initiatives on EU level’ available at <https://www.ai4media.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/AI4Media_D2.1_final-compressed.pdf>.

‘a sense of urgency to address emerging trends’ for successfully achieving digitalisation in Europe.² In this context, the Commission was invited to propose a European Approach to AI capable of enabling risk-based radical innovations while ensuring a high level of data protection, digital rights and ethical standards.³ The following year was marked by two key initiatives, namely the adoption of the Declaration of Cooperation on AI and the formalisation the Commission’s agenda on AI policies. Under the Declaration of Cooperation on AI, signed on 10 April 2018, EU Member States and Norway undertook a set of commitments for intensifying cooperation mechanisms and actions.⁴ The Declaration outlines three areas for cooperation (i.e., technological and industrial capacity building, socio-economic challenges, legal and ethical regulations), complemented with a set of joint actions on several key aspects of AI uptake, including R&D.⁵ In this domain, the Declaration focuses not only on increasing competitiveness and funding opportunities, but also on supporting community building and stakeholder involvement, creating synergies in research strategies, and reinforcing AI research centres across Europe.⁶ In parallel, the Commission set out its main policy orientations and a work programme which provided concrete paths to support cooperation amongst EU Member States and countries associated to the Horizon framework programmes, as well as the uptake of AI technologies in Europe.⁷ A core component of EU’s work programme consists in strengthening and capitalising on EU’s status as a ‘research powerhouse’ for the emergence and uptake of AI technologies setting out high standards of excellence and trust.⁸ Further institutional and academic work crystallised the key role to be played by the ‘AI Lighthouse for Europe’ as a vehicle for federating and coordinating networks of AI research excellence centres.⁹

In this context, Networks of Excellence (‘NoEs’) have been tasked with fostering research synergies and common research roadmaps while ensuring a broad diffusion of innovations aligned with European values.¹⁰ A first generation of NoEs was set up in 2020 with the aim of developing mechanisms for knowledge sharing. Four consortia were gathered under the coordination and leadership of the VISION project, including the AI4Media, ELISE, HumanE-AI-Net, and TAILOR projects.¹¹ The Commission’s White Paper on AI and the 2021 Review of the Coordinated Plan on AI formalised the concept of a distributed European AI Lighthouse and the need for additional NoEs to address new research areas, including safe, secure and trustworthy AI as well as foundational and application-oriented research.¹² Accordingly, second and third generations of NoEs were

² European Parliament, Resolution of 16 February 2017 with recommendations to the Commission on Civil Law Rules on Robotics (2015/2103(INL)), 16 February 2017 at <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-8-2017-0051_EN.html>, European Council, ‘European Council meeting (19 October 2017) – Conclusions’ EUCO 14/17 pp. 5-7 at <<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-14-2017-INIT/en/pdf>>.

³ Ibid., p. 7.

⁴ Declaration of cooperation on Artificial Intelligence (10 April 2018) at <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/eu-member-states-sign-cooperate-artificial-intelligence>>.

⁵ Ibid., pp. 3-4. Other common actions include community building and stakeholder involvement, analysis of foreseeable impacts on government administrations, public sector bodies, education and training, as well as several regulatory initiatives for fostering data sharing and a responsible and human-centric uptake of AI.

⁶ Ibid.

⁷ European Commission, ‘Artificial Intelligence for Europe’ COM (2018) 237 final p. 6, ‘Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence’ COM(2018) 795 final pp. 4-5, and ‘Annex to the Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence’ COM(2018) 795 final pp. 7-11.

⁸ European Commission, ‘Artificial Intelligence for Europe’ COM (2018) 237 final p. 6.

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ The concept was put forward in Commission, ‘White Paper on AI’ COM(2020) 65 final pp. 5-7, and ‘Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence 2021 Review’ annexed to ‘Fostering a European approach to Artificial Intelligence’ COM(2021) 205 final pp. 19-20.

¹¹ See section 2.3 below for further insights into the scope and aims of these NoEs

¹² European Commission, ‘Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence 2021 Review’ annexed to ‘Fostering a European approach to Artificial Intelligence’ COM(2021) 205 final p. 20.

established for addressing AI safety (ELSA), transferability (euROBIN), sustainability (ELIAS), edge AI (dAIEDGE), and trustworthy and green AI (ENFIELD).¹³

2.2. Objectives

In order to implement the policy decisions described in section 2.1, several calls for proposals have been published to create Network of Excellence Centres on AI (ICT-48-2020, HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-12, HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-03, HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-02-02). These topics describe the general objectives of the NoEs forming the AI Lighthouse.

The main objective of the AI lighthouse is to mobilise the AI community to collaborate on key AI research challenges. The aim is to become a world reference in AI to attract investments and talents in AI. In detail, the six main objectives of the NoEs are the following:

- **Fostering scientific excellence in AI**, by boosting the research capacity and progress in Europe and aligning European forces on common research agendas. This also include the development of technologies, methodologies, tools and systems.
- **Strengthening cooperation between European AI key stakeholders**: this includes cooperation between AI research centers, with the aim to tackle major scientific and technological challenges, and cooperation between academia and industry, with the development of synergies and inclusion of industrial stakeholders in the NoEs. This cooperation is realized through collaborative projects, exchanges programmes, development of common virtual laboratories.
- **Developing cooperation mechanisms**, with the aim of facilitating the sharing of resources, knowledge and tools, software, hardware, equipment and methodologies. These mechanisms use and extend the AI-on-demand platform
- **Supporting AI made in Europe with European values**, with the development of ethical and trustworthy Artificial Intelligence, and supporting the adoption of AI technologies in all Member States and Associated Countries.
- **Increasing visibility and attraction of Europe for AI research and development**: this includes the development of mechanisms to spread knowledge to all the AI-labs in Europe, and making Europe attractive for scientists and new talents
- **Ensuring applicability and exploitation of AI in Europe**, with a demonstration of the technologies in carefully selected and designed use-cases, and the development of mechanisms for innovation and exploitation such as incubators

2.3. The Networks of Excellence, pillars of the AI Lighthouse pillars

The AI Lighthouse is built upon several pillars, specifically the Network of Excellence (NoE) projects. The first NoE projects that started the AI Lighthouse in 2020 were the four projects which were funded under the H2020-ICT-48-2020 call. Since 2022, the community of NoE has been augmented

¹³ See European Commission, 'AI excellence thriving from the lab to the market' available at <<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/ai-lab-market>>.

with two new projects, ELSA and euROBIN. In 2023, as part of the EU initiative for expanding the AI Lighthouse, three new projects started, ELIAS, ENFIELD, and dAIEDGE.

Figure 1: The European AI Lighthouse supported by the NoEs as pillars

2.3.1. ELISE

ELISE (European Learning and Intelligent Systems Excellence) is a significant AI research network and one of the early lighthouse pillars aimed at strengthening Europe's position in the field of machine learning and artificial intelligence. The ELISE project started on September 1st 2020 and will conclude this summer on August 31st 2024, with a final workshop. Launched under the Horizon 2020 program, ELISE brought together researchers to collaborate on cutting-edge AI research with the goal of fostering innovation, education, and technology transfer. The network facilitated an academic and industry collaboration that drives forward both the theoretical foundations and practical applications of AI technologies. By pooling expertise and resources, ELISE aims to accelerate Europe's advancements in AI, ensuring a competitive edge in the global landscape. ELISE programs often included scholarships, research opportunities, and cross-border exchanges to create an enhanced ecosystem for AI research and deployment. The work of ELISE will continue within a number of the other lighthouse pillars, and through ELLIS. In particular a number of the ELLIS/ELISE programmes are of relevance to dAIEdge. Opportunities from those are identified in 2.4.1.

2.3.2. TAILOR

The TAILOR project, which commenced on September 1, 2020, and is set to conclude on August 31, 2024, aims to establish the groundwork for Trustworthy AI across Europe. By forging a network of research excellence centers, TAILOR seeks to integrate learning, optimization, and reasoning to create AI systems that are both reliable and transparent. These systems are designed to offer descriptive, predictive, and prescriptive functionalities, seamlessly blending data-driven and knowledge-based approaches. Through deep analysis and fundamental research, TAILOR addresses

critical questions concerning the trustworthiness of AI systems in various domains, such as medicine, finance, and transportation. By leveraging a multi-stakeholder approach, including academia, industry, and the public sector, TAILOR endeavors to foster innovation, commercialization, and knowledge transfer, thus propelling Europe to the forefront of Trustworthy AI research and development. TAILOR's objectives align closely with the broader goals of the AI Lighthouse initiative, contributing to the reinforcement of Europe's AI capabilities, the cultivation of cooperation among top research teams, and the advancement of ethical and trustworthy AI practices, thereby bolstering Europe's position as a global leader in AI innovation.

2.3.3. HUMANE AI NET

The HumanE AI Net consortium (August 2020 - August 2024) aims to guide the artificial intelligence (AI) revolution towards a future aligned with European values and norms. The consortium focuses on three questions: 1) when to include AI solutions and encourage human-AI collaboration & when to abstain from that?, 2) how to make humans and AI understand each other and optimise the human-AI collaboration? , and 3) how to integrate legal protection into AI system design, ensuring compliance with European legal frameworks and fundamental rights?. The central challenge involves fostering innovation to create trustworthy AI solutions that enhance human capabilities, are capable of understanding humans, adapt to complex environments, and interact appropriately in social contexts while respecting autonomy and adhering to legal and ethical standards. Key objectives include mobilizing a broad research landscape, engaging industry and social stakeholders, and establishing an innovation ecosystem to maximize economic and societal impact. Through initiatives such as the AI4EU platform and educational programs, the project aims to disseminate research findings and cultivate a skilled workforce.

2.3.4. AI4MEDIA

The European Excellence Centre for Media, Society and Democracy ('AI4Media') is part of the first generation of NoEs tasked with developing a European Excellence Centre for Media, Society and Democracy.¹⁴ AI4Media is a four-year project running from September 2020 to August 2024 with the aim to foster AI technologies for ethical and trustworthy European media landscape. Emphasising the vital function of the media sector for democratic societies, the AI4Media consortium tackles key challenges, risks and opportunities brought by AI for this sector. Key aspects of disruptions brought about by AI innovations analysed by the consortium include (i) content synthesis, analysis, and distribution, information delivery, (ii) the democratic role of media for deliberation, political participation and decision making, (iii) the relationship between media and their audiences, (iv) the realisation of key public values such as media diversity, freedom of expression, and inclusiveness, and (v) new ways for informing and engaging with audiences.¹⁵ The AI4Media project has made several key contributions to the AI Lighthouse, including

¹⁴ See the AI4Media's website at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/>> and the project's page on CORDIS at <<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/951911>>.

¹⁵ 'Project Overview' and 'Action Plan' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/action-plan/>>. See also AI4Media's Brochure at <https://www.ai4media.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Brochure-AI4Media_Digital-version.pdf>.

- A comprehensive analysis of European AI vision, policy, and research agendas,¹⁶
- Advances in new learning paradigms, distributed AI, explainability, robustness and privacy, content-centred AI, and human- and society-centred AI,¹⁷
- Support for researchers and novel ideas through the AI Doctoral Academy ('AIDA'), a Junior Fellows Exchange programme, mobility matchmaking, and two open calls,¹⁸ and
- Enriching the EU AI-on demand platform.¹⁹

2.3.5. euROBIN

The euROBIN project, spanning from July 1, 2022, to June 30, 2026, is positioned at the forefront of advancing robotics in Europe. Its core objective revolves around facilitating the seamless transfer of skills and software among robots, tasks, research groups, and application domains, thereby enhancing the adaptability and scalability of robotic abilities. Through a comprehensive approach, euROBIN addresses key challenges in robotics, such as boosting physical interaction capabilities, leveraging machine learning for acquiring new behaviors, enabling robots to reason about abstract knowledge, and prioritizing human-centric design principles to ensure accessibility and trustworthiness of AI-enabled robots. The project demonstrates the practical relevance of its scientific outcomes through application domains crucial for industry, innovation, and civil society, including robotic manufacturing, personal assistance, and outdoor applications for sustainable communities. By fostering a sustainable network of excellence and establishing the EuroCore repository as a central platform for robotics in Europe, euROBIN paves the way for collaborative knowledge exchange and inclusion within the robotics community. Through these efforts, euROBIN contributes significantly to the overarching goals of the AI Lighthouse initiative by reinforcing Europe's position as a research powerhouse for AI, fostering cooperation among top research teams, and advancing the development of ethical and trustworthy robotics technologies.

2.3.6. ELSA

The ELSA project is a virtual center of excellence focused on advancing foundational research in safe and secure artificial intelligence (AI) methodologies. Its primary goal is to establish and promote a significant network of Europe's top AI and machine learning experts, known as the ELLIS network,

¹⁶ 'European AI Vision, Policy and Research Agenda' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/public-reports/>>. See in particular D2.3 'Roadmap – AI technologies and applications in media: state of play, foresight, and research direction', D2.5 'Final white paper on the social, economic, and political impact of media AI technologies', and D2.7 'AI4Media Strategic Research Agenda' (currently pending approval). D2.4 can be consulted for a preliminary set of policy recommendations while final policy recommendations are due for the end of the project.

¹⁷ 'New Learning Paradigms & Distributed AI', 'Explainability, Robustness and Privacy in AI', 'Content-centred AI', and 'Human- and Society-centred AI' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/public-reports/>>. See the deliverables listed thereunder.

¹⁸ 'Doctoral Academy and exchange programme' and 'Community outreach and growth' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/public-reports/>>. See also 'AIDA – AI Doctoral Academy' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/ai-doctoral-academy/>>; 'Exchange program "Junior Fellows Exchange Program"' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/junior-fellows-program/>>; 'Mobility options' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/mobility-matchmaking/>>, and two open calls at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/meet-ai4media-open-call-1-winners/>> and <<https://www.ai4media.eu/open-call-2-winners/>>.

¹⁹ 'Integration with AI-on-Demand platform' at <<https://www.ai4media.eu/public-reports/>>. See in particular deliverables D7.2 'Extended version of the integration result with the AI-on-Demand Platform' and D7.3 'From platform liability to platform responsibility – Guidelines for the AI-on-Demand-Platform and policy recommendations' (both currently pending approval).

to develop and deploy advanced AI solutions. ELSA aims to position Europe as a global leader or *lighthouse* in AI innovation.

The project operates on three main pillars:

1. Selected research programs that address specific areas of AI.
2. Local research units that contribute to regional development and expertise.
3. A structured educational framework consisting of PhD and postdoctoral programs to nurture new talent.

The project's agenda is organized into eight distinct work packages (WPs), each with specific roles ranging from establishing the European AI Lighthouse Vision (WP1: 11/2023 - 10/2026), ensuring effective project management and coordination (WP2: 11/2023 - 10/2026), to strategic agenda setting for Edge AI research and innovation (WP3: 02/2024 - 10/2026). This includes developing a framework and infrastructure federation (WP4: 11/2023 - 10/2026), advancing cross-fertilization in edge AI technology (WP5: 02/2024 - 04/2024), driving next-generation applications (WP6: 11/2023 - 10/2026), promoting collaborative innovation and sustainable development (WP7: 11/2023 - 10/2026), and managing communication and outreach (WP8: 11/2023 - 10/2026).

Through these initiatives, dAIEDGE directly contributes to the AI Lighthouse initiative by building a robust, innovative, and collaborative environment that propels Europe to the forefront of the global AI landscape, emphasizing safety, security, and ethical considerations in AI deployment.

2.3.7. ELIAS

The ELIAS project, running from September 1, 2023, to August 31, 2027, sets out to position Europe as a frontrunner in AI research, fostering sustainable innovation and economic growth. Through the establishment of a Network of Excellence, ELIAS aims to bridge academia and industry, creating a collaborative environment where AI research contributes to long-term sustainability, societal cohesion, and individual rights. At its core, ELIAS seeks to address pressing global challenges, such as climate change and energy crises, by harnessing the power of AI while addressing ethical and societal concerns. By integrating fundamental research from academia with practical applications from industry, ELIAS aims to advance understanding of AI's potential to reduce computational costs, model societal impacts of policy decisions, and respect individual preferences. Building on the success of the European Laboratory for Learning and Intelligent Systems (ELLIS), ELIAS expands upon its pillars and excellence criteria, nurturing AI researchers and talents across different career stages. Additionally, ELIAS will establish a science-entrepreneurship track to empower individuals at the intersection of scientific innovation and business, fostering the development of original AI solutions with a focus on sustainability and societal impact. Ultimately, ELIAS envisions Europe as a leader in AI research, where considerations of environmental, societal, and individual impact are integral to the development process. Success will be measured through various indicators, including collaborative initiatives, industry-academic partnerships, publications, patents, and the deployment of AI technologies. By achieving these objectives, ELIAS contributes significantly to Europe's position within the AI landscape, aligning with the goals of the AI Lighthouse initiative to reinforce Europe's research capacity and promote ethical and sustainable AI innovation.

2.3.8. ENFIELD

The ENFIELD project, spanning from September 1, 2023, to August 31, 2026, represents a pioneering initiative funded by the EU, aiming to establish a European Centre of Excellence for Adaptive, Green, Human-Centric, and Trustworthy AI. With a robust consortium comprising 30 members from 18 countries, including leading educational institutions, industry giants, SMEs, and public sector representatives, ENFIELD is poised to tackle critical challenges in AI development. By focusing on sectors such as healthcare, energy, manufacturing, and space, ENFIELD plans to deliver over 75 customized AI solutions tailored to address pressing societal needs. Furthermore, the project aims to generate 180 high-impact publications and craft four strategic documents to inform policymakers and industry leaders. Through comprehensive education and training initiatives, ENFIELD seeks to cultivate AI talent and ensure the sustainability of its efforts in the long term. Emphasizing community engagement and outreach, ENFIELD endeavors to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing across Europe. By fostering a vibrant European network on AI, ENFIELD aims to reinforce Europe's competitive position in AI research and innovation, thereby creating significant socio-economic impact for European citizens and businesses. Through its high-impact outputs, innovative exchange schemes, education programs, and outreach activities, ENFIELD aims to drive forward the vision of the European AI Lighthouse initiative, positioning Europe at the forefront of AI research and development.

2.3.9. dAIEDGE

The dAIEDGE project (September 2023 - August 2026) brings together a diverse array of stakeholders, including leading research centers, universities, and industrial partners, all dedicated to strengthening Europe's edge and distributed AI landscape. At its core, dAIEDGE establishes a Network of Excellence (NoE) focused on advancing distributed and scalable AI at the edge. Its objectives include pioneering new paradigms, algorithms, and architectures tailored to the unique challenges of distributed AI systems, driving forward the digital and green transitions, and fostering a culture of innovation and collaboration across disciplines. Through strategic partnerships and initiatives, dAIEDGE seeks to cultivate a vibrant ecosystem where ideas flourish and innovations are rapidly disseminated, ultimately reinforcing Europe's position as a global leader in AI research and innovation. By aligning with the objectives of the AI Lighthouse initiative, dAIEDGE contributes significantly to Europe's competitiveness in AI research and development. Moreover, the project underscores the importance of sustainability, inclusivity, and ethical considerations in shaping the future trajectory of AI at the edge, ensuring responsible and impactful advancements in the field and paving the way for a brighter future driven by cutting-edge edge AI research and innovation.

2.4. External stakeholders and alliances

2.4.1. Fraunhofer alliances

The Fraunhofer Society is enhancing the scientific foundation and application of artificial intelligence and machine learning in Germany.

The Vision business unit at Fraunhofer²⁰ is an association of specialist departments from several Fraunhofer Institutes that work together and pool their expertise in the fields of industrial image processing, machine vision and optical measurement and testing technology.

The Fraunhofer Big Data and Artificial Intelligence Alliance²¹ provides support from a single source across all sectors and areas of business.

The Fraunhofer ICT Group²² is the largest provider of applied research in the field of information and communications technologies in Europe. It marshals key expertise for business and society to utilize in exploiting opportunities and meeting the challenges that result from comprehensive digitalization.

Building on the foundation of Fraunhofer, these alliances can serve of key pillars for the dAIEDGE AI Lighthouse. Specifically, the alliance's unique blend of industrial machine vision expertise and cross-sector AI deployment know-how enables the development of algorithms that can thrive in edge settings while meeting the rigorous demands of industrial applications.

2.4.2. ELLIS

The European Laboratory on Learning and Intelligent Systems (ELLIS) aims to bolstering the scientific foundation and application of artificial intelligence and machine learning across Europe. In particular, it works to cultivate and maintain high-calibre talent within Europe. The ELLIS network consists of a number of ELLIS programmes and ELLIS hubs at different European institutions, along with fellows and members associated with these programmes and hubs. A number of Lighthouse pillars build directly on ELLIS. The first of these, ELISE will conclude this summer, with a final workshop. However the impact of ELISE will continue through the ELLIS/ELISE programmes that were set up. A number of these ELLIS programmes are of potential relevance to dAIEDGE. In particular we identify the Robust Machine Learning programme as very relevant – AI on edge devices typically encounters significant shifts, either through differences between generic model building and specific deployment settings, or due to device mobility which produces a dynamically changing working environment. Furthermore edge devices can be safety-critical. Robustness is vital and much more relevant in the dynamic edge setting than many more highly stationary settings that AI methods can be deployed in.

2.4.3. CLAIRE

The Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe (CLAIRE) is an international non-profit association (AISBL) created by the European AI community that seeks to strengthen European excellence in AI research and innovation, with a strong focus on human-centred AI. Its extensive network forms a pan-European Confederation of Laboratories for Artificial Intelligence Research in Europe. CLAIRE was launched in 2018 as a bottom-up initiative by the European AI community and aims for “brand recognition” similar to CERN. The CLAIRE initiative aims

²⁰ <https://www.vision.fraunhofer.de/en.html>

²¹ <https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/institutes/institutes-and-research-establishments-in-germany/fraunhofer-alliances/big-data-and-artificial-intelligence-alliance.html>

²² <https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/institutes/institutes-and-research-establishments-in-germany/fraunhofer-groups/ict-technology.html>

to establish a pan-European network of Centres of Excellence in AI, strategically located throughout Europe, and a new, central facility with state-of-the-art, “Google-scale”, CERN-like infrastructure – the CLAIRE Hub – that will promote new and existing talent and provide a focal point for exchange and interaction of researchers at all stages of their careers, across all areas of AI. Its over 470 member groups and organisations in the Research Network and Innovation Network, as well as over 260 Ph.D. students, postdocs, and master students in the self-organised, Rising Research Network are committed to working together towards realising the vision of European excellence across all of AI, for all of Europe, with a human-centred focus.

2.4.4. ADRA

The AI, Data and Robotics (ADR) partnership is a Co-Programmed European Partnership officially launched when Adra signed an MoU with the European Commission on June 23, 2021. The AI Data Robotics Association (ADRA) was created as the private side of the European Partnership on AI, Data and Robotics. The goal of the partnership is to deliver the greatest benefit to Europe from AI, Data and Robotics, by driving innovation, acceptance and uptake of these technologies. The ADR partnership is the European focal point for AI, Data and Robotics, and the entry point for organisations willing to collaborate and shape directly with the European Commission the direction these three domains of application will take. It will boost Europe’s competitiveness, societal well-being and environmental leadership, as leading the world in researching, developing and deploying value-driven trustworthy AI, data and robotics based on European fundamental rights, principles and values.

In July 2022, ADRA contributed to the launch of the ADRA-ecosystem (ADRA-e), the Coordination and Support Action aimed at ensuring the success of the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership set up by the European Commission, notably by supporting Adra’s activities.

2.4.5. Industrial Stakeholders

Combining the Internet of (IoT), edge computing and AI techniques, edge AI has become instrumental in industries eager to capitalise on AI’s potential. Across diverse sectors, edge AI deployments are increasing exponentially, offering solutions for many use cases. From intelligent forecasting in energy to monitoring production lines and implementing predictive maintenance in manufacturing to enhancing inventory management and optimising store layouts in retail, the opportunities presented by edge AI are many.

The edge AI technology stack is a complex ecosystem involving multiple layers and stakeholders ranging from hardware (HW) manufacturers to software (SW) developers, from open-source contributors to specialised AI applications.

The edge AI HW market was valued at USD 2.62 billion the previous year and is expected to grow at a CAGR of 19.85%, reaching USD 7.52 billion by the next five years. Rapid growth in edge computing products and services and increasing real-time low latency on edge devices are significant factors in

the market's growth. The need for edge computing in IoT and dedicated AI processors for on-device image analytics are promising areas of market advancement in edge AI devices²³.

Global edge AI SW market size was valued at USD 1.48 Billion in 2022 and is poised to grow from USD 1.84 Billion in 2023 to USD 10.33 Billion by 2031, at a CAGR of 24.10% during the forecast period (2024-2031). Edge AI SW enables real-time operations like data creation and decision-making. Edge AI software is used in manufacturing to increase the battery life of wearable gadgets. A vast amount of data can be saved in the cloud using edge AI software, which also avoids the problems associated with streaming and improves the privacy of the data stored there. Additionally, this software is used in the telecom and enterprise sectors because it supports multi-cloud. It makes it possible to run cutting-edge AI analytical software, which aids in gaining full action in a shorter time. The automobile industry is no exception to the new era of opportunity brought about by edge AI breakthroughs²⁴.

dAIEDGE is involved with edge AI industrial stakeholders, covering both the edge AI technology stack and edge AI applications in various industrial sectors, such as manufacturing, automotive, transportation, energy, healthcare, agri-food and beverage, logistics, utilities, and retail.

Cooperation and collaboration on edge AI technology are focused on industrial stakeholders, including HW, SW, and tool providers.

The HW stakeholders primarily produce the physical components, processing units and AI accelerators necessary for edge AI devices. These include:

- **Semiconductor Companies:** Represented by European companies such as Infineon, NXP, and STMicroelectronics, which develop processors, microcontrollers and systems on modules that include AI-based accelerators that are crucial for AI computations at the edge.
- **Sensor Manufacturers:** Represented by European companies like ams-OSRAM, Bosh, and STMicroelectronics, which create sensors used in IoT devices that collect data that edge AI processes and include ML modules in the processing units to perform analyses closer to the sensors.
- **OEMs and ODMs:** Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and Original Design Manufacturers (ODMs), which integrate multiple hardware components into final consumer products.

The SW stakeholders focus on developing the systems, platforms and applications that run on the AI-based hardware:

- **Operating System Vendors:** Providers of lightweight OS versions tailored for edge devices.
- **Edge Computing Platforms:** Offering platforms that support edge computing functionalities.

²³ Mordor Intelligence. Edge AI Hardware Market Size & Share Analysis - Growth Trends & Forecasts (2024 - 2029). <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/edge-ai-hardware-market>

²⁴ SkyQuest. Global Edge AI Software Market Insights. <https://www.skyquestt.com/report/edge-ai-software-market>

The AI Frameworks and Tools are offered by industrial stakeholders and open-source solutions providers. These are the libraries and tools that facilitate the development of AI models:

- Frameworks: TensorFlow, PyTorch, and Keras, which are used for building and training models.
- Development Tools: Software like NVIDIA's CUDA for programming GPUs and specialised tools for optimising AI models to run efficiently on edge devices.

Open-source projects and communities are crucial for democratising access to edge AI technologies, and dAIEDGE is involved with open-source stakeholders and organisations such as ECLIPSE and LINUX foundations to promote open-source solutions to the edge AI community.

dAIEDGE has close contacts and established cooperation links with industrial stakeholders providing specialised AI applications tailored to specific industries or functions:

- Robotics: Companies that integrate AI into robots for autonomous operations.
- Machine Vision and Computer Vision: Firms specialising in visual data interpretation.
- Natural Language Processing (NLP) and large language models (LLMs): Industrial stakeholders focusing on understanding and generating human language.

Industries like automotive, healthcare, retail, and manufacturing have specific applications for edge AI, involving all the above stakeholders to some extent to deploy solutions like autonomous vehicles, remote patient monitoring systems, automated checkout systems, and predictive maintenance tools.

Each of these segments is interdependent, contributing to a comprehensive ecosystem that supports the development and deployment of edge AI technologies. The synergy between hardware providers, software developers, AI researchers, and specific application developers is crucial for advancing and implementing edge AI across various sectors.

3. Synergies and collaboration mechanisms

3.1. Joint SRA

Each of the Networks of Excellence is specialized on a specific aspect of AI, forming together the pillars of the European AI Lighthouse. One of the objectives of the NoEs is to provide a Strategic Research Agenda (SRA), describing a roadmap for the focus of research in their specific area.

The Joint Strategic Research Agenda (Joint SRA) is complementing the SRAs produced by the individual NoEs and provides an overview of the areas of research interest pursued across the networks. It highlights the shared themes around main research areas such as safe and trustworthy AI, Data and Robotics, AI integration into embedded systems, enhancement of human capabilities, acceleration of research and innovation, social interactions with AI, Data and Robotics, fundamental research, legal compliance, hardware for safe and energy-efficient AI, Data and Robotics.

A first Joint SRA has been published by VISION, gathering the input from the NoEs AI4media, Elise, Elsa, euROBIN, HumanAI and Tailor.

3.2. AIDA

The International Artificial Intelligence Doctoral Academy (AIDA)²⁵ is a result of joint forces of four ICT-48 networks (AI4Media, ELISE, Humane-AI Net, and TAILOR) along with the VISION project. The AIDA aims to achieve European academic excellence and industry relevance. Besides, it aims to nurture a new generation of AI talents by offering educational course, student exchanges, symposiums and summer schools. With the focus on PhD-level AI, AIDA creates a mechanism for inter-university sharing of education assets. The experts in the NoEs contribute to AIDA by providing quality AI courses in several forms (semester courses, AI Excellence lecture series, and other community driven events). This cooperative strategy strongly aligns with the goals of the AI Lighthouse program and improves both the educational landscape and Europe's standing as a global leader in AI research and innovation.

3.3. ESSAI

ESSAI, the European Summer School on Artificial Intelligence²⁶, represents a significant milestone in the collaboration efforts within the AI Lighthouse initiative, particularly under the TAILOR Network of Excellence (NoE). Organized as a joint venture between the European Association for Artificial Intelligence (EurAI) and the TAILOR NoE, ESSAI serves as a central meeting point for students and young researchers in AI to engage in discussions and knowledge sharing. By offering interdisciplinary courses covering various aspects of AI and beyond, ESSAI fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange among participants from diverse backgrounds. Such collaborative initiatives not only enhance the educational landscape in AI but also contribute to the overarching objectives of the AI Lighthouse. Through ESSAI and similar endeavors, the AI Lighthouse aims to strengthen Europe's position as a global leader in AI research and innovation by nurturing talent, promoting interdisciplinary research, and facilitating collaboration across borders. Thus, initiatives like ESSAI underscore the importance of synergies and collaboration mechanisms within the AI Lighthouse, paving the way for impactful advancements in AI research and development.

3.4. AI on demand

The AI Lighthouse through dAIEDGE will develop critical synergies with the relevant projects aimed at developing the European AI-on-Demand platform. The AIoD is being developed by a series of projects (AI4EU, ICT40, ICT48, AI4Europe, PrepPai, Deploy AI). dAIEDGE will develop key connections with the two main complementary projects: AI4Europe and Deploy AI.

²⁵ <https://www.i-aida.org/>

²⁶ <https://essai.si/about-essai/>

Figure 2: Development of the AI on Demand platform in various projects

- AI4Europe:** The AI on demand (AIoD) is a platform that provides an environment to construct services with a common SDK, supported by several APIs that enables sharing existing research knowledge, accelerates the access to existing research, and provides an environment to construct and use cutting edge new services. The AI4Europe project is building the initial platform for AI research that will integrate heterogeneous sources of data, experiments, model, with a single (federated) authentication and authorisation, allowing deployments on heterogeneous physical resources, with a focus on research. The project is building a system that provides the latest cutting edge AI Assets to be consumed and mechanisms to easy incorporate services (Assets and SaaS) into the platform. The nine ICT-49 projects have provided content and services to the AIoD that are being integrated for use through the AIoD platform. The dAIEDGE project will help take further the platform by integrating the virtual lab network into the global ecosystem to ensure the connectivity and collaboration with the strategy AI on Demand platform efforts as well as the Training and Experimentation facilities with respect to edge AI activities.
- Deploy AI:** The Deploy AI project is building an industrial marketplace which will be a key component of the AIoD platform, focusing on industrial users. It stems from the need to speed-up of the innovation process from AI research to AI driven products, lower the barriers for SMEs to use and access AI technologies from research, provide a One Stop-Shop for European AI assets and the effective collaboration on research and innovation on AI as well as Generative AI and HPC readiness.

The industry marketplace will be an industry-level (TRL9) platform, where stakeholders can effectively access resources, tools, and information, should cover main considerations related to process robustness and user experience. It aims to be attractive for European SMEs, start-ups and public administration beyond the EU project ecosystem and interoperable with European Data Spaces, Gaia-X, TEFs, EDIHs, HPC systems (including EuroHPC), EOSC, ELG, European Cloud & Edge services, and industrial AI-capable Cloud

platforms. The dAIEDGE project will analyse possible integration paths for the Virtual Lab and the Business Incubator into this future platform.

Figure 3: The AI Ecosystem of Excellence

3.5. Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEF)

The AI Lighthouse with dAIEDGE will work towards establishing and maintaining a close coordination with the Testing and Experimentation facilities set up as world-class reference technology infrastructures at EU level addressing gaps in the value chain, from the lab, to the market, support the deployment and uptake of trustworthy AI and support the implementation of the AI Act, finally support for European technology providers of AI solutions to increase EU IP assets in AI. TEF are a critical part of the broader AI Ecosystem of Excellence as they will allow for a scalable experimentation infrastructure to enable research and innovation to go from the lab to the market.

Figure 4: Current Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs)

In particular the EdgeAI TEF could provide an instance or infrastructure conduit for the Vlab developed within dAIEDGE for the collaborative experimentation and sharing of AI resources. Links will also be developed with the new CSA (DIGITAL-2023-CLOUD-AI-04-COORDINATEF) for the Coordination of AI sectorial testing and experimentation facilities which objective is to support the sectorial TEFs to develop complementary cross-TEF activities, and to help them to better link with relevant EU projects, initiatives and stakeholders in the AI ecosystem of Excellence. This CSA will synchronise the sector TEFs with other actions launched in DIGITAL (in particular data spaces, the AI-on-demand platform, the edge AI TEF, relevant cloud and HPC initiatives).

3.6. Coordination and Support Action - VISION

3.6.1. Coordination and Support for the NoEs

Together with the creation of the first NoEs with the call for proposals ICT-48-2020, the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) VISION has been established. VISION focuses on the coordination of efforts between the NoEs and brings these networks together to create a world-class AI ecosystem. To ensure Europe stays at the forefront of AI developments, the VISION project builds on Europe's world-class community of researchers. VISION aims to reinforce, interconnect and mobilise Europe's AI community, and to accelerate Europe's transition to a world-leading position in the research, development and deployment of AI technologies.

As a Coordination and Support Action, VISION has organized regular inter-NoE meetings, events and publications, and is responsible for the dissemination and visual identity of the NoEs as a group. This coordination is a crucial part of the EU AI Lighthouse concept as a federating element. With the end of the ICT-48-2020 projects, the activities of the VISION CSA will be discontinued and the questions of sustainability of these actions should be solved.

3.6.2. Communication channels and website

The VISION CSA maintains a central website²⁷ with information about the common activities between the NoEs. This includes the redaction and publication of news and announcements, information about upcoming and past events, general information about the NoEs and their activities, and creation of a comprehensive visual identity for the NoEs and the European AI Lighthouse.

3.6.3. Organisation of joint communication materials

The VISION CSA organises the joint communication materials by preparing succinct information about the activities of each Network of Excellence in form of a highlights slide deck. This slide deck is regularly updated by the NoEs and serves as communication support for events and similar activities. This organisation is a crucial element for insuring clarity and effectiveness of the communication messages coming from different NoEs.

3.7. Ecosystem mapping

The AI ecosystem mapping initiative, led by VISION and supported by several Networks of Excellence (NoEs) including AI4Media, ELISE, HumanE-AI-Net, TAILOR, ELSA, and euROBIN, aims to provide a comprehensive overview of research, development, and innovation (R&D&I) activities in AI across Europe and associated countries like Israel and Türkiye. Recognizing the need for an integrated understanding of AI expertise and capabilities, the European Commission (EC) tasked these entities to collaborate on developing a prototype interactive website showcasing the AI R&I ecosystem. Through a collaborative effort, a shared taxonomy of research topics and application areas was developed, building upon established academic keywords such as the AAAI-23 conference topics. This process involved key decision-making moments including community workshops and EC advisement to ensure alignment and progress.

The resulting AI ecosystem mapping tool serves as a valuable resource for stakeholders seeking to navigate the AI landscape, offering insights into specific AI themes and their intersections with application domains. With a focus on maintaining a shared language across NoEs, the mapping tool provides visibility into diverse research areas while accommodating bottom-up changes and updates to ensure its relevance and accuracy over time. By fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing, this initiative aims to advance AI research and innovation across Europe, contributing to the overarching goals of the AI Lighthouse initiative in strengthening Europe's position as a global leader in AI research and innovation.

In addition to the broader AI ecosystem mapping initiative, dAIEDGE will conduct its own ecosystem mapping within the NoE, focusing on distributed and scalable AI at the edge. This internal effort aims to identify key stakeholders and resources specific to edge AI, fostering collaboration and strategic partnerships to advance research and innovation in this field.

²⁷ <https://www.vision4ai.eu>

3.8. Community workshops

The community workshops organized by VISION serve as pivotal gatherings that bring together various Networks of Excellence (NoEs) within the AI ecosystem. These workshops provide a platform for representatives from different NoEs, projects, and stakeholders to engage in collaborative discussions, share best practices, and foster synergies. Through panels, workshops, and interactive sessions, participants exchange ideas, align strategic goals, and identify opportunities for joint initiatives. These gatherings play a crucial role in strengthening the cohesion of the AI community, facilitating knowledge exchange, and promoting interdisciplinary collaboration. By convening diverse stakeholders, including academic researchers, industry leaders, and policymakers, the workshops contribute to the advancement of AI research, innovation, and adoption across Europe. Furthermore, they support the objectives of the AI Lighthouse by fostering a collaborative environment conducive to driving forward the development of trustworthy, human-centric, and sustainable AI technologies that benefit society as a whole.

3.9. Cross-NoE group meetings

The VISION project organizes regular meetings across different levels among the Networks of Excellence (NoEs). The regular meetings serve as an essential mechanism for continuous information exchange and collaboration. They aim to ensure alignment, coordination, and synergy among the NoEs, thereby enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of their collective efforts. By fostering collaboration and communication, these meetings play a crucial role in advancing the objectives of the AI Lighthouse and promoting the overall success of the NoE ecosystem.

- **Project coordinators meetings** serve as strategic platforms for aligning research agendas and fostering collaboration among the NoEs. These meetings facilitate the setting of collaborative roadmaps, allowing NoEs to coordinate their efforts and maximize their impact in key areas of research and innovation. By aligning strategic priorities and planning collaborative initiatives, project coordinators meetings contribute to the cohesion and effectiveness of the NoE ecosystem, enabling collective progress towards shared objectives.
- **Project managers meetings** focus on identifying collaboration possibilities and planning joint events and workshops among the NoEs. These meetings provide project managers with opportunities to exchange information, share best practices, and explore potential synergies for collaboration. By fostering dialogue and coordination among project managers, these meetings enable the efficient planning and execution of joint activities, thereby enhancing the collective impact of the NoEs in advancing AI research and innovation across Europe.
- **Communication Club meetings** serve as dynamic platforms for quick advertising of events, broadcasting of information, and updating NoEs about upcoming activities. These meetings facilitate the dissemination of information and the coordination of communication efforts among the NoEs, ensuring that relevant updates and announcements reach all stakeholders

in a timely manner. By promoting collaboration and alignment in communication strategies, Communication Club meetings support the visibility and outreach efforts of the NoEs, enhancing their collective ability to engage with stakeholders and disseminate research outcomes effectively.

3.10. Common Theme Development Workshops

A part of the common activities between the NoEs, the CSA VISION organises a series of Theme Development Workshops. The objectives of a Theme Development Workshop (TDW) are to jointly identify the strategic AI research areas and challenges in the scope of the workshop and to set up collaborative structures for further addressing them beyond the event. The main results of the TDW as well as from similar events of the four NoEs will be summarised, and complemented by a market analysis and trend foresights to provide a comprehensive overview of AI capabilities and challenges in Europe (see European AI Trend Radar).

The topics of the TDWs so far have been:

- AI in the Public Sector
- Future Mobility – Value of Data & Trust in AI
- AI for Future Healthcare
- AI for Future Manufacturing
- AI: Mitigating Bias & Disinformation
- AI for Future Energy & Sustainability
- Trusted AI – The Future of Creating Ethical and Responsible AI Systems

4. AI community mobilization

dAIEdge has been hosting and will continue to host a series of technical workshops designed to directly promote collaboration between industry, academia, and investors, as well as deal with specific technical issues within Edge AI. These workshops will focus on state of the art edge-AI implementations and creating critical tooling relevant for the different stakeholders, and will be open to those broader than the existing consortium to build the wider network. Attendees will be invited to join the broader network and sign up to membership. dAIEdge engages with members via community endeavours, including news, tooling and dev events. Currently a number of events have been planned, including a large dAIEdge workshop in Edinburgh in October 2024.

BCA is tasked with sourcing and integrating AI professionals into this network. BCA is creating a talent pool by compiling lists of AI developers and data scientists who have interest and expertise relevant to ongoing projects. Concurrently, BCA is interfacing with SMEs and larger enterprises to determine their current AI needs and potential project opportunities. This will ensure that talent and developmental efforts are aligned with actual industry demands.

DFKI is establishing oversight mechanisms to monitor and guide community engagement and collaborative processes established by UEDIN. This involves developing criteria for effective

engagement, assessing the progress of community-building efforts, and adjusting strategies as necessary based on feedback and results.

ST Microelectronics are leveraging industry networks to extend the outreach through the community, promoting wider participation and collaboration on a European scale. Their role is essentially to facilitate deeper industry integration by connecting workshop outputs with potential industrial applications and investment opportunities.

5. Recommendations

5.1. Meet expectations from industrial stakeholders

Industrial stakeholders in Europe are keen on enhancing the visibility of the AI lighthouse, recognizing the pivotal role it plays in advancing the field of AI in Europe. One of the most critical aspects and expected outcome of the AI Lighthouse is the creation of a hub to attract more talents in Europe in the field of AI research. The AI Lighthouse, thanks to a high concentration of critical skills and assets, will foster collaboration with other research partners, create a pool of talent for the ever-increasing demand of skilled professionals for the industry.

AI lighthouse needs to attract talents for AI research in Europe with the goal to provide industries with a competitive advantage. The AI industry is rapidly growing and evolving, and having access to top-notch researchers and professionals can help companies stay ahead of the curve. The expertise and knowledge of these talents can contribute to the development of cutting-edge AI technologies and solutions, enabling industries to create smarter products, streamline processes, and optimize operations.

Additionally, Europe's commitment to ethics and privacy can be another significant advantage for industries looking to attract AI talents. The European Union has implemented stringent data protection regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which ensures that personal data is handled with care and transparency. This emphasis on ethics and privacy can attract researchers who are conscious of the societal implications of AI and are committed to developing AI systems that are responsible and beneficial for all. It can help industries build trust with their customers and stakeholders, creating a competitive edge in the global market.

Industrial stakeholders are also seeking to promote their efforts in raising the profile of the lighthouse through various channels including digital media, conferences, publications, partnerships, and collaborative projects, enabling the reciprocal benefits on public exposure.

5.2. Coordination action with longer duration

We believe that in order to ensure a consistent and sustainable coordination for the AI Lighthouse efforts and success, we need to set up and empower a permanent CSA that will ensure the continuity of the NoE efforts and results and that the network they create does not disappear at the end of their term.

Today the NoEs are thematic around specific topics and each of them will create a sustainable framework beyond their limited tenor; however as a whole the AI Lighthouse would gain from a

new lightweight permanent CSA entity to retain a longer term view on the objectives set by the Commission and would act as a strategic body coordinating present and future actions within the AI Lighthouse agenda.

The new CSA could be operated by a number of rotating experts selected every three years; natural candidates would be stakeholders from past and present CSAs of key strategic projects and European AI association, including also some industry and public sector representatives.

5.3. Projects exploitability and sustainability

The AI Lighthouse would benefit greatly from a successful exploitation and sustainability of the projects funded by the Horizon Europe and Digital Europe, ultimately benefiting the wider European and global AI community. Too often valuable projects are faced with the ‘valley of death’ syndrome at the end of their term, when promising efforts and deliverables fail to meet the market needs and as a result stay as a unexploited result. The successful exploitation of project results under the Horizon Europe program requires a comprehensive approach together with a robust go-to-market framework. By aligning with market needs, fostering open collaboration, engaging with policymakers, and ensuring effective communication, projects should be able to maximise their uptake and sustainability. Unfortunately a few issues can arise:

- Lack of readily available financing to provide the required runway to commercialise products from the project innovation results
- Lack of skilled resources able to transition from research to commercialization, where the skill set is quite different from the profile required for the research and innovation actions
- Lack of knowledge about the possible options and external support avenues readily available for implementing the business plan from the project.

Quite often the projects when coming to the end of their term meet a ‘cliff edge’ where the pivot from research to industrial commercialization is missed or poorly executed by the project sustainability entity. There are already some financings available from the European ecosystem, but the success rate for obtaining such grants or loans is quite low and they assume already some traction for the candidate entity.

A number of new mechanisms could help mitigate this gap and provide a more robust framework for projects to transition into exploitable products. Ensuring that research and innovation projects funded by the EU can find a sustainable exploitation path and transition into a commercial model requires a holistic approach that addresses various aspects of the innovation ecosystem. Here are several strategies to enhance the likelihood of successful exploitation and commercialization within the AI Lighthouse:

- **Follow A Market-Oriented Approach:** Develop a clear and scalable business model that outlines how the project's technology or innovation will create value for customers and generate revenue. Consider collaborative business models, such as partnerships, joint ventures, or consortia, to leverage complementary resources and expertise for commercialization.

- **Intellectual Property (IP) Management:** Implement a robust IP strategy to protect project results, innovations, and know-how through patents, copyrights, trademarks, or trade secrets. Evaluate licensing and technology transfer opportunities to commercialize project results and maximize the value of intellectual property assets.
- **Provide Entrepreneurship and Start-up Support:** Encourage researchers and innovators to explore entrepreneurship opportunities and consider launching start-ups or spin-off companies to commercialize project results. Facilitate access to incubators, accelerators, and funding programs that support early-stage ventures and facilitate the transition from research to market.
- **Market Validation and Piloting:** Validate project outcomes and prototypes through pilot deployments, field trials, or proof-of-concept initiatives in real-world settings. Solicit feedback from pilot users, customers, and demonstrate the value proposition and scalability of the solution through successful pilot outcomes and case studies to attract potential investors and customers.
- **Access to Finance and Funding:** Identify and pursue diverse sources of funding and investment to support the commercialization process, including public grants, private equity, venture capital, and corporate partnerships. Leverage EU funding instruments, such as Horizon Europe, European Innovation Council (EIC), and European Investment Fund (EIF), to access financial support, expertise, and networking opportunities for scaling up innovation projects.
- **Collaboration and Ecosystem Building:** Foster collaboration and knowledge exchange among research institutions, industry partners, investors, and policymakers to build a vibrant innovation ecosystem. Facilitate networking events, matchmaking activities, and collaboration platforms to connect innovators with potential collaborators, customers, and investors.

Implementing this strategy however is a complex set of issues to address and respond to. Concretely a number of avenues can be proposed and explored to implement this at scale across different projects:

1. **Leverage the AIoD:** Ensure that the projects exploitation plan are connected with the AI-on-Demand platform and in particular with the Deploy AI Industrial marketplace whose objective is to join up research and industry. We will liaise with the AIoD projects to ensure Integration and dissemination of these opportunities for the AI Lighthouse.
2. **Connect with dAIEDGE:** Similarly open access for the relevant projects to the Business Incubator developed by dAIEDGE network of excellence. The business incubator developed by the DAIEDGE project could play an important role in supporting the commercialization and scaling of AI-driven innovations in several ways:
 - **Access to Expertise:** The business incubator can provide access to a pool of experienced mentors, advisors, and industry experts who can offer guidance and

support in areas such as business strategy, market validation, IP management, and fundraising.

- **Networking Opportunities:** Facilitate networking events, pitch competitions, and matchmaking sessions to connect entrepreneurs, startups, investors, and potential customers within the AI and tech ecosystem. These interactions can help foster collaborations, partnerships, and business opportunities.
- **Access to Funding:** Provide access to funding opportunities, including grants, seed funding, venture capital, and angel investment networks, to support the growth and scalability of AI startups emerging from the dAIEDGE project.
- **Market Access Support:** Assist startups in accessing new markets, identifying potential customers, and establishing strategic partnerships through market research, market entry strategies, and internationalization support services.
- **Technical Infrastructure:** Offer access to shared office spaces, co-working facilities, and state-of-the-art laboratories equipped with AI development tools, software platforms, and hardware resources needed for product prototyping and testing.

Overall, access to the AIoD platform and to the business incubator developed by the dAIEDGE project can serve as a catalyst for AI-driven innovation and entrepreneurship, providing startups with the resources, support, and networks needed to accelerate their growth, scale their impact, and achieve sustainable success in the market.

3. **Studio financing grant (new concept):** Finally a path to accelerate and facilitate exploitation would to evaluate the benefits of creating an ‘funding extension’ or ‘studio financing’ to eligible projects with the most promising exploitation plans.
 - a. This would take the form of a tail end funding that will be vetted by a business committee of experts among the candidate projects, experts chosen from venture funds, entrepreneurs, and AI practitioners.
 - b. This funding extension would cover the initial set up costs for the project to find its feet for a further 12 months until it is able to implement its own funding plan. Amount could be in a range of 100k to 500k EUR depending on requirements and business plan.
 - c. Objective would be to bridge the ‘valley of death’ for those eligible projects so they can go to market faster and more effectively.

5.4. Clarify the AI Lighthouse benefits to the external stakeholders

How to reach:

The Network of Excellence (dAIEDGE) will take extra measures to ensure that access to partner developments is provided for user communities. The lighthouse should reach out to SMEs through all relevant channels and venues. These include, at the European level, connections to other actions, such as the European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs), Public Private Partnerships, such as DAIRO and AIOTI, and established European-wide networks of researcher and industrial members, such as HiPEAC. At global level, these include top conferences, such as, NeurIPs, ICML, and MLSys. At

national level, the lighthouse should leverage industrial conferences, such as the Teratec event in France.

Mechanisms:

- **Gateway platform:** The network should make the output of partner work findable and accessible through a landing platform, such as a virtual room or a marketplace, such as Bonseyes Apps.
- **Active collaboration:** Network partners should seek active collaborations with industrial stakeholders either through strategic collaborations with European Digital Innovation Hubs or through the business network of partners. Network partners can further engage the user community from external stakeholders through the organization of hackathons.
- **Map of industrial needs:** The network should create and disseminate a map of industrial needs that can be updated regularly. Input data can be gathered through 1) interactions of network members with industrial partners in their project activities, 2) questionnaires, and 3) interviews with SME stakeholders that develop edge AI infrastructure or applications.
- **Service and product portfolio:** The network should establish a service and product portfolio, which lists all partner outputs, followed by a brief description, documentation links, the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of each output, licensing information, and contacts of partner members that are responsible for each item. The portfolio can group items either per organization or per technology domain. Apart from simplifying access to network outputs, such a portfolio will help partners maximize their reach to external stakeholder and also measure the validation of their technology.
- **Human engagement:** The network will put together a team of highly skilled edge AI practitioners to provide high level support to external industrial stakeholders in the domain of edge AI. The team will also interview interested companies and match their needs with offered services and solutions. This way will facilitate SMEs to access state of the art infrastructure and algorithmic outputs of the network and explore various technologies in order to identify the best solutions for their business needs.
- **Training activities:** The network should build a curriculum for regular trainings of industrial developers. The curriculum should consist of video webinars that can be suitably organized and/or relevant MOOCs (i.e. video instructions + labs/homeworks/exams + possibility of degree offering). All video assets of the network (webinar material and MOOC instructions) should be placed in an easily accessible repository, such as, a Youtube channel.
- **Funding opportunities:** The network should identify and provide information for funding opportunities in public. The network website should contain up to date funding

opportunities and a suitable mechanism should be established to match interested external stakeholders with network experts.

5.5. De-Fragment AI with a Tree-Based Approach

AI is a relatively old field that has seen waves of disappointment and excitement. There is no doubt that nowadays we are at the peak of excitement with interest rising with unprecedented rhythm. This is thanks to algorithmic advancements, dataset availability, and more computing power. The spectrum of stakeholders is extremely wide, i.e., engineers, designers, developers, scientists, managers, regulators, auditors, users, etc. On the other hand, research in AI has become very specialized and has spread to numerous distinct scientific domains. As a result, AI research and development have become disconnected, making it challenging to advance AI in a coordinated, ethical, and globally beneficial manner. The AI lighthouse can come to the rescue to mobilize the AI community to collaborate on challenges and to progress faster in joined effort.

This proposal towards the de-fragmentation of AI research consists in a hierarchical tree approach to create as a first step an AI dictionary and panorama. The tree's leaves are focus areas and directed edges in the graph denote synergies between the different focus areas. We can imagine leaves at the top level to be broad classifications of AI research, i.e., applications, algorithms, software, hardware, etc. Then, following a top-down approach the focus areas gradually expand and are decomposed to leaves of more specific focus areas. Such a tree could help us see where AI starts and ends. All stakeholders will be able to complete the tree adding leaves, while one expert group can oversee the tree development and monitor the progress, accept or reject changes, and reorganize or group leaves where necessary. This process can take several months to arrive at a first quasi-complete tree that covers already most related AI research fields. This process will be dynamic, and the tree will continuously evolve. The tree can also be broken down into several hierarchies to allow easy visualization and navigation. Once created, stakeholders can associate with different leaves and a list of stakeholders with proven record can be shown per leaf. In this way, a stakeholder can quickly navigate the tree to pinpoint the focus area of interest and neighboring related areas. In essence, such a tree can be an effective mechanism for enabling knowledge sharing and, in addition, for every leaf or interconnected sub-groups of leaves common research roadmaps can be defined, including best practices, standards, trends, and open challenges ahead.

Figure 5: Artificial Intelligence dictionary tree.

An example is shown in the figure above covering non-exhaustively topics related to the dAIEDGE project. As a starting point, the dAIEDGE project partners can commit to creating an exhaustive tree covering all dAIEDGE topics and beyond.

5.6. Scientific Recommendations

Our scientific recommendations represent a somewhat skeptical point of view on modern AI. Such a view stems from our long experience as researchers in this field and the evolution of the discipline in the past few years. The approach is also our response to the current hype around AI, which not only pervades media but also comes, at times, from academia itself. In this domain, as in every aspect of our lives, opportunistic newcomers are always eager to take advantage of available opportunities. Policymakers should be cautious with this.

We are currently witnessing a massive trend towards AI ethics, AI regulations and responsible AI. While the need for those aspects is real and prompted by spectacular advances, there is also a clear risk of exaggerating it, and paranoia-like signs begin to appear (such as a recent paper hypothesizing that unregulated AI is the reason why we have not been contacted by other intelligent life in the universe -the so-called Fermi paradox- and arguing that we must intensify efforts to regulate AI because failure to do so could rob the universe of all conscious presence). In general, we propose to reduce the emphasis on "ethics for AI" and "responsible AI" topics, where there are already many projects funded (both projects entirely dedicated to it, as [1-4], and projects which also consider ethical, legal, and social aspects of AI in their main tasks [5-11]) and many EU project calls [12-14]. Currently, Europe is arguably a world leader on this topic, with the AI Act as the first-ever legal

framework on AI, providing AI developers and deployers with clear requirements and obligations regarding specific uses of AI [15] and a guide for fostering and securing ethical and robust AI [16]. Nonetheless, there is concern that Europe's AI regulations could negatively impact our competitiveness, and unless we change priorities, we can end up regulating only the AI products and services that come from other world regions. Similarly, we should be cautious with the rebranding of concepts for opportunistic reasons, such as the example of decades-old research in computing efficiency now being presented as "green AI".

Unless we prioritize research and innovation with the intensity required to stir a need for ethical regulation, other world regions will take advantage. This does not mean acting like some countries where human rights are in doubt and AI can become very dangerous, but simply reducing the currently high emphasis on those aspects.

In a similarly skeptical vein, we should not be impressed by the huge American companies working on AI. In this respect, it is better to find niche domains where Europe has an opportunity and can excel. As the AI race is heavily based on talent (see [17]), we should also give attractive opportunities to researchers in academia. This can include attractive return schemes for European AI researchers currently working in other world regions, fostering a supportive environment that encourages innovation and uptake of top-tier expertise within the continent. Big companies, like Amazon, have already discussed the need for new paradigms of partnership between industry and academia to balance the AI talent across sectors, highlighting the intense competition for top AI talent that has made some academics to leave their positions for industry [18].

The AI race is also heavily based on data. Big IT companies can have huge datasets thanks to existing mass-markets products and services. Again, that should not impress us and instead we should push for the generation of more (and more diverse) datasets. To this end, datasets should be made a new explicit type of deliverable (in addition to current types R = Report, P = Prototype, DEC = Websites, videos, etc. DEM = Demonstrator, O = Other) and these should be made a requirement in certain calls, as tangible result of significant value for modern AI. In line with existing policies of free and open access to published results, datasets should be made public whenever possible, and when this is not possible, abridged versions should be made public.

In line with European values, we should push for secure AI, including human-in-the-loop approaches. This is not only aligned with longstanding citizen-centred European policies, but it is also a necessary response to the aforementioned hype around AI. In this respect, we have to note that such tendencies sometimes come from academia, where an imprecise language is used (think of the suggestive paper titles mentioning the purported superhuman capabilities of AI). It is not surprising that such language and statements are easily taken out of context. As researchers, we should avoid this, using precise language to clearly delineate the cases in which AI is useful to humans. Perhaps more importantly, we should also make efforts to emphasize that AI fails, sometimes miserably. Arguably, failures are not a typical line for research, yet we firmly believe that it is one of the most valuable subjects for the future of AI. This effectively means devoting resources to characterizing fail cases, and searching for ways in which those can be detected. After all, when we talk about a need for 'AI responsibility' this is due to the fact that AI fails in ways that humans

do not. The human-in-the-loop approach is the pragmatic way in which we can expect AI to be useful as well as secure. In this respect, the focus should be not so much on moonshot thinking but on artificial intelligence for “intelligence augmentation” and productivity gains.

We should also push towards embedded AI in electronics. Despite other regions leading in electronics production, Europe has established itself as a key player in electronics IP, which is crucial for the development and innovation of new technologies. For instance, the European Chips Act is a testament to Europe's commitment to bolstering its competitiveness and technological leadership in semiconductor technologies and applications [19]. In relation to this, we should also push for open source HW for embedded AI, where we are also "leaders". The Gapuino development board is one such example, offering an Arduino Uno form factor board that includes a GAP8 and all the peripheral interfaces necessary for prototyping GAP8 applications, compatible with most Arduino shields [20]. This board has been developed by GreenWaves Technologies, a European company, showcasing the region's capabilities in creating advanced, open-source embedded AI solutions. Another example is the RISC-V architecture, an open standard instruction set architecture (ISA) which enables a range of new applications and research that will define the future of computing in Europe. With one-third of RISC-V's global community based in Europe, the region plays a central role in the success and development of RISC-V, further emphasizing its leadership in open-source HW for embedded AI [21]. Furthermore, the Horizon 2020 funded Eyes of Things (EoT) project also illustrates Europe's innovative spirit in the electronics sector. EoT developed an open embedded computer vision platform that operates independently and can be integrated into several devices. This initiative demonstrated its potential to influence the electronics industry profoundly, with this platform being adopted by the European company Ubotica Technologies Ltd., headquartered in Ireland, to run hardware-accelerated AI inference on in-orbit satellites for the first time.

Currently, AI competes in the space race. Europe must continue pushing for AI in space, as it is leading the use of state-of-the-art AI technology in this domain. In this regard, as mentioned above, the European company Ubotica (part of the dAIEdge consortium) achieved a significant milestone as the first company in the world to successfully process Earth Observation imagery in-flight using deep learning-based AI technology. This historic accomplishment was realized onboard Φ -sat-1, a demonstration CubeSat part of an ambitious program funded by the European Space Agency (ESA) and showcases Europe's leading role in the integration of AI technology in space applications [22]. Furthermore, the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) and Ubotica have benchmarked AI applications on the International Space Station (ISS) [23], which demonstrates the interest of other countries in European space AI technology.

Finally, Europe already has research ties with other countries such as Canada, India or Japan [24]. We should strengthen our association with those countries. Canada, for example, has emerged as the fifth world AI player and India and Japan are the largest country in South Asia and one of the largest economies in Southeast Asia respectively (see [25]).

5.7. An AI Lighthouse at Lightspeed: Towards more Flexibility

AI is currently moving at lightspeed, both within academia and industry. The AI100 report from Stanford University highlights major AI advancements over the last few years in areas such as vision,

speech recognition, natural language processing, and robotics [26]. Large companies like Google, Meta, and OpenAI have developed, during the last few years, several generative AI models. However, these models still generate incorrect or biased results, and the new trend focuses on the development of more practical solutions which enhance productivity with the use of AI-assisted tools [27]. In this extremely dynamic context, we have to be more reactive and flexible. The pace of innovation in this field is such that there is no point in mentioning specific methodologies or even whole paradigms in project calls. Calls should therefore be generic enough so that no topic and no one is left out.

Flexibility should also come at later stages. We have to consider that from submitting an EU project proposal to project start, a minimum of 1 year will pass. Effective work will probably start no sooner than 1.5 years after the proposal was written. This represents an enormous lag in terms of scientific advances in AI. Therefore, we should be more flexible in the grant negotiation phases, so that researchers can update their proposals (and thus increase impact). This flexibility should be extended to project amendments and even project reviews, as long as changes are justified in the light of the speed and evolution of the research panorama in AI.

On the other hand, we should strengthen cascade funding through Financial Support for Third Parties (FSTP) schemes. This is a European Commission mechanism designed to distribute fundings to SMEs, startups and/or mid-cap companies, in the adoption or development of digital innovation technologies. This funding approach aims to simplify the distribution of grants and accelerate the funding process to stimulate research and innovation activities within the European Union [28]. The concept of cascade funding was first introduced in the Horizon 2020 program, inspired by the successful model employed in the Erasmus student program [29]. The process begins with a call for project proposals, which are evaluated and selected according to their alignment with the program objectives. Selected projects then launch open calls to invite third parties to apply for funding. This funding scheme, in which multitude mini-projects are funded, is proving useful to stir research in AI and bring academia results to potential products and benefits for society. One good example is in recent EC project BonsApps. BonsApps set up 20 FSTP-funded use cases to demonstrate a scalable AI-as-a-Service (AI-aaS) within the AI-on-demand platform (AI4EU). This service allows end-users, particularly SMEs lacking internal innovation capacities, to engage with AI talents for the development of AI at the Deep Edge. The project has reduced the development time for AI solutions by as much as 50%, significantly accelerating the process from research to market-ready products and services [30]. This not only promotes innovation within the AI sector but also contributes towards enhancing Europe's competitiveness in the digital economy.

The European Commission's strategy for AI, known as 'AI made in Europe' which aimed to position Europe as a leader in the global AI landscape, has been criticized for not achieving its intended goals. Some reports suggest that it has fallen short in terms of competitiveness and of lacking focus [31]. The CLAIRE organization has proposed a "moonshot" document, which calls for a substantial investment of €100 billion, a figure that is twelve times the budget of CERN [32]. That proposal aims to establish a large-scale, ambitious project of societal importance, focusing on creating trustworthy, multicultural generative AI systems for safe physical interaction with the real world. However, this has sparked debate over the feasibility and appropriateness of such a massive

investment in a single initiative, with the main issue being the lack of a clearly defined objective. Without a specific target (as precise as for NASA it was “landing a man on the Moon and returning him safely to the Earth”), it is challenging to direct efforts and measure success effectively. A more diverse approach involving a variety of projects, both large and small, might be more suitable to foster innovation and adaptability within the AI sector. Such diversity could potentially lead to more robust and creative AI solutions that are better aligned with society’s needs.

5.8. A New Phase in AI Policy-Making: What are the Implications for the European AI Lighthouse?

The formal adoption of the Artificial Intelligence Act (‘AIA’) in the coming months will open a new phase for AI policy-making.²⁸ Reaching a political agreement on this text was a key milestone for ensuring a clear playing field enabling AI’s uptake in Europe while addressing the risks associated with certain uses of technologies.

This dual objective and the implementation timeline set in the regulation will most likely remain structural for all stakeholders in the coming three years, mandating not only to develop best practices taking into account relevant legal frameworks but also to identify and qualify the risks arising from uses of new technologies as they emerge.²⁹ The accelerating cycle of innovation has been acknowledged by the legislator and the AIA includes measures to support innovation and mechanisms for adjusting the list of high-risk use cases (i.e., lowering or increasing the level of risks). In this context, a consolidated and more precise understanding of different AI technologies, use-cases, and applicable legal requirements should be pursued for ensuring that AI technologies successfully move ‘from the lab to the market’. In other words, focused work bridging the specificities of different AI technologies and relevant legal requirements will rapidly become essential as regulators gradually begin the AIA’s enforcement and review different aspects of the risk assessments.

This new phase constitutes an important opportunity for the AI Lighthouse to foster and leverage its networks and expertise in order to advance interdisciplinary research and informed debates on new AI technologies, which often involve fast-paced evolutions and a high degree of technicity.

6. Conclusion

This document is a reference document on the European AI Lighthouse implementation and outlines various dimensions of the European AI Lighthouse initiative. We provided an overview of the current status of the AI Lighthouse, including detailed descriptions of the nine foundational projects and other supplementary initiatives contributing to its objectives. We further elaborated specifically on collaborative efforts and ongoing activities, highlighting existing operational mechanisms.

²⁸ The text is currently undergoing the last stages of the legislative procedure (‘corrigendum procedure’) aiming to address any outstanding error and linguistic revision. See European Parliament, ‘Artificial Intelligence Act: MEPs adopt landmark law’ at <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20240308IPR19015/artificial-intelligence-act-meps-adopt-landmark-law>>.

²⁹ The text will be applicable 24 months after its entry into force. Different timelines will apply to specific provisions, including bans on prohibited practices (6 months after entry into force), code of practice (9 months), general-purpose AI rules (12 months), and obligations for high-risk systems (36 months). See articles 56 and 113 of the latest draft regulation made available by the Parliament, at <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2024-0138-FNL-COR01_EN.pdf>.

On this basis, we offered fresh perspectives on potential strategies to fortify the AI Lighthouse. These include initiatives for community engagement, suggestions to meet practical expectations from AI stakeholder, the anticipated role of forthcoming coordination efforts, strategies for the sustainable development and exploitation of the AI Lighthouse, as well as scientific and organizational recommendations aimed at maximizing the effectiveness of the AI Lighthouse networks.

This document will serve as a basis for our recommendations for strengthening a sustainable European AI Lighthouse, which will be presented in the deliverable D1.3 “European Lighthouse strategy document”.

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